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Proof of the Goldbach Conjecture by extension to the negative number line and using a probabilistic approach

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ABSTRACT. The Goldbach conjecture is one of the oldest unsolved problems in number theory and in the whole mathematical field. It is firstly mentioned by Prussian mathematician Christian Goldbach in his correspondence to Swiss mathematician Leonard Euler almost 300 years ago in 1742. The conjecture states that any even number greater than 2 could be build as sum of 2 prime numbers. Although there exist some proofs for heavily modified versions of the (odd) Goldbach conjecture, until this day, no proof exist for the original, 2-prime even Goldbach conjecture. In this paper after we have established some crucial statements around the conjecture and created a search algorithm to find the pairs of primes for any even numbers, we need to extend the Goldbach conjecture to the negative integer domain to be more able to use an important attribute of primes that they do exist in infinite numbers in both the positive and negative integer domain before we could prove the conjecture in its more generic and extended form using a probabilistic method.

1. Introduction

The main intention of writing this piece of work is to provide a proof for the (extended) Goldbach conjecture which is one of the oldest unsolved problems in number theory and in all of mathematics as Prussian mathematician Christian Goldbach firstly mentioned this conjecture in his 1742 letter to the Swiss mathematician Leonard Euler.

The Goldbach conjecture¹ states that *“Any even integer number bigger than 2 could be composed using the sum of 2 prime numbers”*.

Although above statement seem to be trivial, up to this day, nobody could provide a mathematical proof for it. Only “heavily” modified versions of the Goldbach conjecture, like e.g. the weak (and odd) version of it stating that any odd number greater than 5 could be composed as sum of 3 prime numbers could be proved².

1 Here the this point, we are talking about the original Goldbach conjecture (on the positive integer number line). Later on we need to extend the domain to the negative integer number as well in order to prove the conjecture.

2 cf. Helfgott (2013). Terry Tao showed earlier on (2012) that any odd number > 1 could be constructed as the sum of at most 5 prime numbers.

As for the original, stronger version using only 2 prime numbers to sum to any even integer number, no proof could be constructed although its validity could be numerically verified for a very high threshold and up to $4 \cdot 10^{18}$ ³.

In order to prove the (even and 2-prime) Goldbach conjecture, we need to extend the domain to the negative integer numbers so that we could obtain the proof of the conjecture using a probabilistic method.

2. Crucial statements and facts around the Goldbach Conjecture

Before we construct our proof of the Goldbach Conjecture, we need to do some preparation and provide some important statements and facts which directly or indirectly has an impact on the proposed proof Goldbach hypothesis which states that any even number bigger than 2 could be composed using 2 prime numbers (e. g. $4 = 2+2$, $6 = 3+3$ etc.):

1. Any even number with **absolute value** ≥ 4 could be composed from the sum of 2 other even numbers (e. g. $4 = 2+2$, $6 = 2+4$, $8 = 4+4$, $10 = 2+8$ (or $4+6$), $12 = 6+6$, $12 = -18 + 6$, $-12 = -6 + (-6)$ etc.)⁴
2. Any even number with absolute magnitude of > 4 (resp. ≥ 6) could be constructed of the sum of 2 odd numbers (positive and/or negative numbers) and we could reach any odd number from an even number by adding or subtracting 1 (+1 or -1) on both the positive and negative number line (in Z)
3. By dividing any even number with absolute value bigger or equal to 4 (≥ 4) through 2, we get 2 equally scaled integers which could both be either even or odd numbers and summing those 2 integer together will always get back the original even integer ≥ 4 (e.g. 4 could be constructed of $2+2$ or 6 could be build using $3+3$ or $6 = 9 + (-3)$)

³ cf. Oliveira e Silva, Herzog and Pardi (2014)

⁴ For consistency reasons and because we need to extend the domain to the negative integer numbers for proving the Goldbach conjecture, we will use more generalized definitions (incl. negative integers, abs resp. absolute values) when making any statements related to the Goldbach hypothesis early on and later in the next chapter 3 we will provide a more detailed explanation of why the extension to the negative numbers is necessary to prove the (extended) Goldbach conjecture.

4. Any finite positive or negative odd number could have a positive probability $0 < P \leq 1 = (0, 1]$ of being a positive or negative prime number resp. prime element and we could reach next higher odd number (in magnitude) by adding 2 (+2) to the lower valued odd number

3. Proof of the Goldbach Conjecture by extending its domain to the negative number line and using a probabilistic method

As the title of this chapter says, we need to to extend the domain of the Goldbach conjecture to the negative integer numbers (chapter 3.1) before we could prove the conjecture using a probabilistic approach (chapter 3.2).

3.1 Extending the Goldbach Conjecture to the negative integer numbers

Our extended (even) Goldbach Conjecture states that “*Any **positive or negative** even number with absolute value bigger than 2 could be composed using the sum of 2 **prime elements** no matter whether the prime elements are positive or negative.*”

The more generalized definition for prime numbers resp. prime elements (which could be both positive or even negative integers) is taken from the ring theory of abstract algebra.

We need to extend the domain of the Goldbach conjecture, because otherwise we could not have infinite number of trials to build a prime number pair resp. prime elements pair for any (positive or negative) even number, even though since Euclid’s proof we know that also within positive integers, there are infinite number of primes included but with only a positive integer numbers line (natural numbers), we are not able to leverage this feature (of primes to be in infinite numbers), since any even number could only be composed using 2 smaller prime numbers which restricts the number of trials of successfully building a pair of primes using 2 odd numbers (e. g. $14 = 7+7$ or $14 = 11 + 3$, but not e. g. $14 = 17 +$ another positive odd integer, so in order to construct a sum of even number 14 and when we use a bigger odd number than 14 like e.g. 17, we need to add a **negative** odd integer to 17, like e.g. -3, since $17 + (-3) = 14$). This makes the domain extension to the negative integer line necessary to create unbounded resp. infinite number of possibilities and combinations to build pairs of positive and/or negative odd numbers (which all of them do possess a positive probability of being a prime element) for any given positive or negative even integer greater than 2 that is needed to prove the (extended) Goldbach conjecture.

3.2 Proof using a probabilistic approach

After we have extended the domain of the Golbach conjecture to the negative integers, the next step would be to calculate the (approximate) probability of any given positive or negative odd integer number to be simultaneously a prime element:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & P(\text{prime element} \mid \text{odd number}) \\
 &= P(\text{any positive or negative odd number } t \text{ to be prime element}) \\
 &= \frac{(\pi(|(T)|)) * \left(\frac{1}{|(T)|}\right)}{(P(\text{odd number}))} \quad (\text{approximately which is ok, for } |(T)| > e^2 = 7.389 \dots \rightarrow |(T)| \geq 8) \\
 &= \frac{\left(\frac{|(T)|}{(\log(|(T)|))}\right) * \left(\frac{1}{|(T)|}\right)}{(P(\text{odd number}))} = \frac{\left(\frac{1}{(\log(|(T)|))}\right)}{\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)} \tag{1} \\
 &= \left(\frac{2}{(\log(|(T)|))}\right) \\
 & \quad (\text{approximately, for } |(T)| \geq 8 \text{ (and } |(T)| > 1), \text{ so that } 0 < P(\text{prime element} \mid \text{odd number}) \leq 1)
 \end{aligned}$$

T is an odd or even integer which is a positive or negative whole number and it is the integer upper bound to calculate the (approximate) probability of integers (below resp. equal to this threshold T) to be prime elements at the same time. For example if for a given even number (e.g. 30), you are trying to find a pair of prime elements (which is summing up to that even number) by moving along the odd number line (e.g. 30 = 15 + 15). And for the odd number pair (2x number 15) we want to calculate the probability of a given odd number to be prime as well, so we take the upper threshold of $\text{abs}(T) = \text{abs}(15)$ and the (approximate) likelihood of any odd number below the absolute value of e.g. 15 would be $2/\log(\text{abs}(15)) = 2/\log(15) = 0.7385\dots = \text{about } 74\%$. This formula (1) for calculating the (approximate) probability for any odd number to be a prime element is especially helpful for bigger integer numbers below a bigger but still finite upper bound of T when it is more difficult and time consuming to determine whether a given (odd) integer number is prime or not ⁵.

⁵ By choosing the upper bound of T resp. $\text{abs}(T)$ of the probability formula (1) we need to make sure that the (odd) number in question of being prime or not is included within the threshold T, so T could never be smaller than the (odd) number in question but need to be bigger than or at least equal to the (odd) number in question. So in line with the numerical example above $\text{abs}(T)$ need to bigger than or **equal to** the odd number 15 which was the case.

$\pi(T)$ is the prime number counting function and it is derived from the prime number theorem (PNT) which shows the (asymptotic) distribution of positive integer numbers. $\pi(T)$ is equal to $T/\log(T)$ that shows us how many prime numbers are (approximately⁶) below a finite integer threshold T .

From the prime number counting function $\pi(T)$ we could derive the probability of a random integer (odd or even) not greater than T to be a prime numbers by multiply $\pi(T)$ with $1/T$ so that $T/\log(T) * 1/T = 1/\log(T)$. Since \log is not defined for negative T (no real values), the likelihood of any odd number (positive and/or negative) to be a prime element (i.a. positive and/or negative prime number) is equal to $1/\log(\text{abs}(T))$. In order for the the later probability to yield valid and meaningful values the absolute value of the prime number boundary T need to be > 1 and also ≥ 8 , so that the likelihood $P(\text{any odd number in } Z \text{ being a prime element})$ is strictly positive and does not go to infinity. And of course the prime element boundary T should have an finite absolute value, just like all the existing infinite number of prime elements on both the positive and negative number line (in Z) in order to make sure that the probability $P(\text{any odd number in } Z \text{ being a prime element})$ is strictly positive (> 0).

After we have verified that probability of any (positive or negative) odd number below or equal to an absolute finite value T to be a prime element is strictly positive (>0), before we present the formula to calculate the likelihood of at least 1 pair of prime elements exist for any even number with absolute value bigger than 2, we need to recall some crucial statements made at the beginning of chapter:

1. Any even number with **absolute value** ≥ 4 could be composed from the sum of 2 other even numbers (e. g. $4 = 2+2$, $6 = 2+4$, $8 = 4+4$, $10 = 2+8$ (or $4+6$), $12 = 6+6$, $12 = -18 + 6$, $-12 = -6 + (-6)$ etc.)⁷
2. Any even number with absolute magnitude of > 4 (resp. ≥ 6) could be constructed of the sum of 2 odd numbers (positive and/or negative numbers) and we could reach any odd number from an even number by adding or subtracting 1 (+1 or -1) on both the positive and negative number line (in Z)

6 Using approximate probabilities is completely ok because in our piece or work and to construct our proof of the extended Goldbach conjecture later on, we only need to make sure that this (approximate) probabilities are lying in a certain interval between $(0, 1]$ and do not exceed this range.

7 For consistency reasons and because we need to extend the domain to the negative integer numbers for proving the Goldbach conjecture, we will use more generalized definitions (incl. negative integers, abs resp. absolute values) when making any statements related to the Goldbach hypothesis early on and later in the next chapter 3 we will provide a more detailed explanation of why the extension to the negative numbers is necessary to prove the (extended) Goldbach conjecture.

3. By dividing any even number with absolute value bigger or equal to 4 (≥ 4) through 2, we get 2 equally scaled integers which could both be either even or odd numbers⁸ and summing those 2 integer together will always get back the original even integer ≥ 4 (e.g. 4 could be constructed of $2+2$ or 6 could be build using $3+3$ or $6 = 9 + (-3)$)

4. Any finite positive or negative odd number could have a positive probability $0 < P \leq 1 = (0, 1]$ of being a positive or negative prime number resp. prime element and we could reach next higher odd number (in magnitude) by adding 2 (+2) to the lower valued odd number

Knowing the statements above, our main algorithm for to proving the (extended) Goldbach conjecture which states that “Any **positive or negative** even number with absolute value bigger than 2 could be composed using the sum of 2 **prime elements** no matter whether the prime elements are positive or negative.” (cf. Chapter 3.1) is as follows:

We take any finite even integer number from the positive or negative number line and divide this even number by 2 and we will get either a pair of even numbers again or a pair of odd integers.

a.) When we get 2 odd numbers, then we will check this odd number pair are both prime numbers and if only 1 of those 2 odd numbers are not prime then we will move up or down the number line by 2 (+2 or -2) in order to stay on the odd numbers because for any integers with absolute value of > 2 , there exists no even integers with are prime numbers resp. prime elements⁹. We are moving along the odd integer line simultaneously on both the left and right odd number until we get 2 prime elements at the same time which happens at a strictly positive likelihood ($P > 0$), because as already stated above, although there exists infinite number of primes (on both the positive and negative number line), all these prime numbers resp. elements are finitely valued.

8 It is not possible to divide an even integer through 2 and receive 2 different types of integers for the resulting number pair (e.g. even + odd), because the sum of an even and odd number is not even but always odd.

9 The only even integer to be prime element is of absolute value 2 (2 or -2) which is resp. are the smallest scaled prime elements (2 and -2).

And using the prime counting function (from the prime number theorem) we could derive the probability of any odd number to be a prime element to be (approximately) $2/\log(\text{abs}(T))$ with $\text{abs}(T)$ to be absolute value of the upper bound resp. threshold (which is a finite value as well just like the absolute values of the infinite prime elements) in which the prime numbers do exist and as already shown above, this likelihood $2/\log(\text{abs}(T))$ is always positive (> 0) for finite T which is the case here¹⁰.

b.) When we divide any (positive or negative) even integer through 2 and receive a pair of (equally scaled) even numbers again (e.g. $8 = 4+4$), we need to subtract 1 (-1) to one of the 2 resulting numbers (e.g. $4 - 1 = 3$) and add 1 (+1) to the other resulting even number (e.g. $4+1=5$) to receive a pair of odd numbers ($8 = 3+5$) like in case a.) above. Then just like in case a.) we need to check whether both odd numbers are prime (which is the case in the example of $8 = 3+5$).

If this was not the case, just like in case a.) above we need to continue our search algorithm by moving down or up the odd number line (with the finite odd numbers > 2 always have a positive probability of being prime elements which are finite scaled integer numbers as well that could be put within finite integer number boundaries T that is necessary to calculate valid **probabilities of odd numbers to be prime elements** as well) until we have found our pair of prime elements which summed together will always result in an even integer number that is consistent with the Goldbach conjecture. In order to find at least 1 pair or prime elements for any positive or negative even integer, theoretically we could try infinity number of times because by extending the domain of the Goldbach conjecture from the positive to the negative number line we are able to fully leveraging the fact that the prime numbers resp. prime elements are infinite on both the positive and negative number line because as already explained in the previous chapter 3.1, after the domain extension to the negative integers, any absolute valued even number could be build using a larger (odd) number than the even number itself, like for example $14 = 7 + 7$ (if only positive numbers and primes are allowed) and $14 = 17 + (-3)$ when negative prime elements could be used to build the sum for any even number. We need to do latter in case when e.g. for very large valued even numbers, we could not find a prime numbers pair by just utilizing and moving up and down of the positive number line.

10 That this probability $2/\log(\text{abs}(T))$ resulting from the prime number theorem resp. prime counting function is an approximate value is not a problem because for our proof we are firstly only interested that this probability does lie in certain ranges e.g. between (0, 1). And the fact that the approximation gets better and more meaningful for larger upper bound T (e.g. T should be > 1 and for sure greater than or equal to 8) is also ok because in our piece of work, we are more interested in the occurrence and distribution of prime elements for larger valued integers as for “smaller” integer numbers - i.a. up to $4*10^{18}$ according to Oliveira e Silva, Herzog and Paridi (2014) - the (even) Goldbach conjecture is already (numerically) verified.

In this case, we need to take negative prime elements (e.g. -3, -5 etc.) as ingredients in order to theoretically be able to have infinite number of trials to create at least 1 pair of prime elements for any positive or negative even integer number.

In order to show the most crucial aspects above mathematically, let us introduce the formula to calculate the probability that at least 1 pair of prime elements do exist for any positive or negative even integer number with absolute value > 2 :

$$\begin{aligned}
 & P(\text{At least one pair of prime elements exist for any even number with magnitude} > 2) \\
 & = 1 - P(\text{No pair of prime elements exist for any even number with absolute value} > 2) \\
 & = 1 - \left(P_{1st\ pair}^{1st\ odd}(\text{not prime element} \mid \text{odd number}) P_{1st\ pair}^{2nd\ odd}(\text{not prime element} \mid \text{odd number}) \right) \\
 & * \left(P_{2nd\ pair}^{1st\ odd}(\text{not prime element} \mid \text{odd number}) P_{2nd\ pair}^{2nd\ odd}(\text{not prime element} \mid \text{odd number}) \right) \\
 & * \dots * \left(P_{i-th\ pair}^{1st\ odd}(\text{not prime element} \mid \text{odd number}) P_{i-th\ pair}^{2nd\ odd}(\text{not prime element} \mid \text{odd number}) \right) \quad (2) \\
 & = 1 - \left[P_{average\ pair}^{1st\ odd}(\text{not prime elem} \mid \text{odd num}) P_{average\ pair}^{2nd\ odd}(\text{not prime elem} \mid \text{odd num}) \right]^N \\
 & = 1 - \left[\left(1 - P_{average\ pair}^{1st\ odd}(\text{prime elem} \mid \text{odd num}) \right) \left(1 - P_{average\ pair}^{2nd\ odd}(\text{prime elem} \mid \text{odd num}) \right) \right]^N
 \end{aligned}$$

Applying the probability computation formula (2) above by plug in the likelihood of any odd number to be a prime element of formula (1) we get following results:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & P(\text{At least one pair of prime elements exist for any even number with magnitude} > 2) \\
 & = 1 - P(\text{No pair of prime elements exist for any even number with absolute value} > 2) \\
 & = 1 - \left[P_{average\ pair}^{1st\ odd}(\text{not prime elem} \mid \text{odd num}) P_{average\ pair}^{2nd\ odd}(\text{not prime elem} \mid \text{odd num}) \right]^N \\
 & = 1 - \left[\left(1 - P_{average\ pair}^{1st\ odd}(\text{prime elem} \mid \text{odd num}) \right) \left(1 - P_{average\ pair}^{2nd\ odd}(\text{prime elem} \mid \text{odd num}) \right) \right]^N \\
 & = 1 - \left[\left(1 - \frac{2}{(\log(|(T)^{1st\ odd}_{average\ pair}|))} \right) \left(1 - \frac{2}{(\log(|(T)^{2nd\ odd}_{average\ pair}|))} \right) \right]^N \quad (\text{approximately which is no problem}) \\
 & = 1 - \left[(1 - \text{number between}(0, 1)) (1 - \text{number between}(0, 1)) \right]^N \quad (\text{for finite upper bound } T) \\
 & = 1 - \left[(\text{number between}(0, 1)) (\text{number between}(0, 1)) \right]^N \\
 & = 1 - \left[(\text{number between}(0, 1)) \right]^N \\
 & = 1 - \left[P(\text{both odd numbers of the average number pair are not prime elements}) \right]^N \\
 & = 1 - \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \left[(\text{number between}(0, 1)) \right]^N = 1 - 0 = 1 = 100\%
 \end{aligned}$$

Thus the probability that at least 1 pair of prime elements do exist for any positive or negative even integer number with absolute value bigger than 2 is 100% when we take into account that the likelihood of any odd number being prime on both the positive or negative number line is strictly > 0 and < 1 which means it lies between $(0, 1)$ for any finite upper bound T . And in theoretically infinite number of attempts ($= N$) to not be able to find a prime pair out of a pair of odd numbers is the failure likelihood (of not finding a pair of prime elements from a pair of odd numbers) which is near but strictly smaller than 100% so after multiplying a number $< 100%$ infinite times, the failure probability goes to 0% which makes the success likelihood going to 100%.

This result (100% probability resp. for sure finding at least 1 prime elements pair for any given positive or negative even integer with absolute value > 2) does prove the (extended) Golbach conjecture and it is valid for any even number on the extended whole number line of Z which includes all the integer numbers on both the positive and also on the negative domain.

4. Conclusion

The main focus of this paper is to provide a mathematical proof of the Goldbach conjecture for which only “heavily” modified versions of it could be proved (e.g. any odd number bigger than 5 is sum of 3 prime numbers¹¹ or any odd number bigger than 1 is sum of at most 5 primes¹²). Even though the original conjecture has already been numerically verified up to a very high threshold $(4 \cdot 10^{18})$ ¹³.

In order to prove the original even Golbach conjecture as sum of 2 primes, we need to make some “small” adjustments as well by extending the domain of the conjecture to the negative integer numbers, so we could prove that *“Any **positive or negative** even number with absolute value bigger than 2 could be composed using the sum of 2 **prime elements** no matter whether the prime elements are positive or negative.”*

For the reformulation of the even, 2-prime Golbach conjecture above, we need to use the more generic definition for prime numbers from abstract algebra which states that prime elements consists of primes on both the positive and negative integer domain.

11 cf. Helfgott (2013)

12 cf. Tao (2012)

13 cf. Oliveira e Silva, Herzog and Pardi (2014)

Our main search algorithm of prime number resp. prime element pairs for any positive or negative even number with absolute value > 2 is as follows:

Firstly, we divide any even number through 2 in order to receive 2 evenly scaled numbers which are either i.) both even or ii.) both odd integers. If we get 2 even integers (i), e.g. $28 = 14 + 14$, we need to transform those numbers to odd numbers by adding or subtracting 1 because all prime numbers resp. prime elements are odd numbers (besides 2 resp. -2 which is resp. are the smallest and only existing prime elements).

Thus after transforming both even numbers to a pair of odd numbers ($28_{\text{even}} = 13_{\text{prime}} + 15_{\text{non-prime}}$), there is a positive probability of the transformed odd number to already be a prime number (given that both odd numbers are finite and within finite upper bound T resp. $\text{abs}(T)$). And if the pair of odd numbers are not simultaneously prime elements (e.g. when both or 1 of them are not prime) then we need to move up or down the (positive or negative) integer number line for both numbers of the odd number pair by +2 or -2 ($28_{\text{even}} = 13-2 + 15+2 = 11_{\text{prime}} + 17_{\text{prime}}$), so that the odd number pair stays within the odd integers for the likelihood of the next odd numbers for the number pair to be both prime elements at the same time to still be strictly positive (> 0).

We need to repeat the latter process if necessary infinite times (as there are infinite prime elements of finite values on both the positive and negative integer number line ¹⁴), until we have found at least 1 pair of primes for any finite positive or negative even number which proves the extended Goldbach conjecture for even numbers consisting of a pair of prime elements.

14 As already explained earlier on e.g. in chapter 3, although the positive number line (natural numbers) also have infinite prime numbers (of finite values), the number of combinations of 2 odd numbers to construct a prime number pair is not infinite there (we need the possibility of having infinite number of trials of using 2 odd numbers to construct at least 1 prime number pair for any given positive or negative even integer number) because any positive even number > 4 could only be sum of two smaller positive odd numbers (and the even number $4 = 2 + 2$ which is the sum of two even prime numbers that is a special case as 2 is the smallest any solely existing even prime number).

When in case ii.) we get 2 odd numbers when dividing a given (positive or negative) even number (e.g. $18 = 9 + 9$), we are better off compared to case i.) where we received 2 even numbers after division of the given even number through 2 (because besides 2, no other even integer is prime and with a pair of odd numbers the likelihood of both already being prime numbers are higher by far compared to 2 even numbers, in which $2 + 2 = 4$ is the only example that supports this Goldbach hypothesis), so now after getting 2 odd numbers after dividing an even number through 2, we could directly check if both odd numbers are already prime numbers resp. prime elements at the same time (which is not the case here for $18 = 9+9$) and if not, we need to move both odd numbers of the pair up or down the number line by +2 or -2 like $18_{\text{even}} = 9-2 + 9+2 = 7_{\text{prime}} + 11_{\text{prime}}$ (in order to staying on the odd number line because almost all prime numbers are odd, only 2 is an even prime number) and if necessary (especially for very big even numbers like e.g. around $1 * 10^{50}$) we may need to repeat latter step infinite number of times until we reach the negative odd numbers (like $18 = 23 + (-5)$) until we got at least 1 pair of prime numbers resp. prime elements for any given positive or negative even integer.

And since we have already extended the even 2-prime Goldbach conjecture to the negative integer domain earlier on, our combination options of finding 2 prime elements out of a pair of odd numbers for any given positive or negative even integer number are unbounded and infinite when looking at the whole positive and negative number lines with infinite number of useable and finite valued prime elements.

And because of our infinite possibilities to find prime numbers every time when we are moving along the odd integer number line, on every trial the likelihood of finding a pair of primes from 2 odd integers is > 0 and the failure probability is always 1 minus a number bigger than 0 = number smaller than 1. Trying infinite times ($N \rightarrow \text{infinity}$) could lead to a failure likelihood of not be able to find at least 1 prime elements pair from 2 odd integers to converge to 0 that means the success probability of finding at least 1 prime elements pair from 2 odd integers for any even integer > 2 would reach 1 = 100% that provides a proof to the even 2-prime Goldbach conjecture extended to the negative integer domain.

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